

Photocatalytic activity of nano sized nickel tin oxide prepared by co-precipitation method

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Abstract : Visible light induced nano sized nickel tin oxide (NiSnO_3) photocatalysts was synthesized by a simple and organic free co-precipitation method from a bath contains equimolar mixture of nickel and tin ions. The crystallographic property of synthesized nickel tin oxide powder was studied using X-ray diffraction technique. The particle size calculated based on the Scherrer equation shows a particle distribution of 87 nm to 118 nm for the nickel tin oxide powder. The formation of the oxide powder was completed above 600 °C as evident from thermo-gravimetric analysis. The photocatalytic activity of the nickel tin oxide was measured based on the degradation of methyl orange in aqueous solution. The results show that nickel tin oxide nano powder exhibit more photocatalytic activity compared to individual addition of nickel oxide or tin oxide and even their mixtures and the rate constant also follows the same trend. The highest rate constant value of $3.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ was observed for the photo degradation of methyl orange with nickel tin oxide as photocatalyst. The photo-bleaching reaction of methyl orange follows the first order kinetics. The enhanced photocatalytic activity of the nickel tin oxide was due to the lower band gap value of the NiSnO_3 compared to SnO_2 and NiO .

Keywords : Photocatalytic activity, band gap, co-precipitation, photodegradation.

Introduction

Titanium dioxide, nickel oxide and tin oxide are widely used photocatalyst in many fields of applications¹⁻³. However, the band gap of these oxides lies between 3.2 to 3.6 eV (TiO_2 – 3.2 eV, NiO – 3.5 eV, SnO_2 – 3.6 eV), these oxides are activated only in UV light which accounts for only a small fraction (~5%) of the solar irradiance compared to the visible region (~45%). The development of visible light driven photocatalyst would therefore be a major advance since it needs only the sunlight for activation. UV active photocatalyst is converted to visible range by lowering the band gap value of the photocatalyst material. The band gap can be lowered by with doping with C, N and S in the crystal lattice⁴⁻⁷. Many coupled transition metal oxides are found to be good photocatalyst under visible light conditions. The photocatalytic activity of nickel titanate⁸, barium titanate⁹, strontium titanate and bismuth titanate^{10,11} were already been reported in the literature. Tin oxide is used in as gas sensors^{12,13}, solar cells^{2,14}, photocatalyst^{15,16} etc. due to its n-type semiconductor nature with band gap of 3.6 eV. Tin oxide having rutile crystal structure similar to rutile titanium

dioxide material, the incorporation of metal oxides in the crystal lattice of tin oxide lattice expected to enable the red shift absorption edge as similar to TiO_2 . In this view, nickel oxide was incorporated to tin oxide powder. The common solid-state method for the preparation of the coupled oxide powder can produce large NiSnO_3 particles with poor compositional homogeneity and uncontrolled structural morphologies. However co-precipitation technique has much advantage over other technique, such as homogeneity in the phase of reactant, stoichiometric control, high purity and ease of processing. The aim of the paper is to synthesize nano sized nickel tin oxide photocatalyst by co-precipitation method.

Experimental

For preparing NiSnO_3 , nickel chloride and stannous chloride were used as the starting material. SnCl_2 (0.2 mol) and NiCl_2 (0.2 mol) are respectively dissolved in 1000 ml of double distilled water. An aqueous solution containing ions of tin and nickel in an equimolar ratio is prepared by admixing 100 ml SnCl_2 solution and 100 ml of NiCl_2 solution. A mixed solution is prepared by ad-

mixing 20 ml of 30% H_2O_2 solution, 15 ml of 28% aqueous ammonia solution and rest of distilled water. To the mixed solution is added dropwise to the aqueous solution containing ions of tin and nickel in an equimolar ratio with stirring to precipitate a complex peroxide corresponding to nickel tin oxide, the precipitate is washed, dried and calcined at 850 °C to obtain nano crystalline NiSnO_3 . X-Ray diffraction was performed on NiSnO_3 powders using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation (Phillips Analytical). Average crystalline size was calculated from the peak width using Scherrer formula. Thermal studies were conducted using TGA Versa thermo-gravimetric analyzer. The photocatalytic decolourization of methyl orange was monitored by measuring the absorbance of light (465 nm) by methyl orange solution with nickel tin oxide powder, exposed to sunlight for different irradiation time, using UV-Visible spectrophotometer of Shimadzu. The initial concentration of methyl orange was 10.0 ppm. During the irradiation time, the solution was bubbled with air.

Results and discussion

XRD studies :

Fig. 1 shows the XRD pattern of NiSnO_3 powders calcined at 850 °C. All the peak values are well matched with nickel tin oxide. The particle size is calculated (Table 1) using the Scherrer formula and it lies between 87–118 nm in size.

Thermo-gravimetric studies :

Thermo-gravimetric analysis of the precipitated sample

Fig. 1. XRD spectra of NiSnO_3 .

Table 1. XRD data of NiSnO_3

Peak at 2 θ	Peak corresponding (radians)	$\beta/2$ (nm)	Particle size
34.1	NiSnO_3	0.001562	87.4
40.2	NiSnO_3	0.001160	118
57.5	NiSnO_3	0.001390	98

is given in Fig. 2. The first step of weight loss was due to the evaporation of water. The second step of weight loss is due to the elimination of hydrogen peroxide present in the nickel tin oxide. On further heating above 500 °C will convert the nickel tin oxide from amorphous phase to crystalline form.

Fig. 2. TG curves of uncalcined NiSnO_3 .

UV-Visible spectral analysis :

Fig. 3 shows the UV-Visible absorption spectrum of the nickel tin oxide. Nickel tin oxide exhibit only one characteristic absorption band, which is assigned to the intrinsic transition from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB). The optical band gap (E_g) was evaluated from the absorption spectra recorded above. The absorption coefficient α is calculate from the spectrum as : $-\alpha = (2.303/d) \log (1/T)$, where 'd' is the thickness of the film. The optical band gap was determined using the Manifacier equation¹⁷ and the band gap of nickel tin oxide calculated was found to be 3.02 eV. The characterisic band gap values reported for NiO is 3.50 eV and SnO_2 is 3.6 eV. The photocatalytic activity of nickel tin oxide is expected to be more due to the lower

Fig. 3. UV-Visible absorption spectrum of NiSnO₃.

band gap value of nickel tin oxide compared to their individual oxides. Illumination of the photocatalyst by photons whose energy is equal to or higher than their band-gap energy absorption of these photons occurs and the bulk of electron-hole pairs generate which is responsible

for the photocatalytic activity of the material.

Photocatalytic measurements :

The photo-degradation of methyl orange by nickel tin oxide is given in Fig. 4. The photocatalytic activity of NiO, SnO₂ and their mixture (1 : 1) is also given in same figure for comparison purpose. The photocatalytic activity of nickel tin oxide was found to be better than nickel oxide, tin oxide and its mixtures. The initial quantity of methyl orange (10.0 ppm) can be represented as 'a' and 'x' is the quantity of methyl orange degraded after photo-degradation for specific irradiation time. The graph drawn by plotting $\ln(a/a - x)$ against time shows a straight line (Fig. 5) with square of regression (R^2) above 0.980 indicates that the reaction follows first order chemical kinetics. The rate constant can be found out from the slope of the graph (Table 2). The highest rate constant was observed for using nickel tin oxide as catalyst ($3.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$) rather than using nickel oxide ($0.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$), tin oxide ($1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$) individually and their 1 : 1 combinations ($2.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$). The enhanced photo-

Fig. 4. Photo-bleaching of methyl orange solution with (●) 0.1% nickel tin oxide, (■) 0.1% SnO₂, (○) 0.1% NiO, (▲) NiO (0.05%) + SnO₂ (0.05%) exposed to sun light for different duration of time.

Fig. 5. A plot of $\ln(a/(a-x))$ against time for photo-bleaching of methyl orange solution with (●) 0.1% nickel tin oxide, (■) 0.1% SnO_2 , (○) 0.1% NiO , (▲) NiO (0.05%) + SnO_2 (0.05%) exposed to sun light for different duration of time.

Table 2. Kinetic data of photo-bleaching of methyl orange solution with different photocatalyst

Photocatalyst	NiSnO_3	$\text{NiO} + \text{SnO}_2$	SnO_2	NiO
Slope	0.01564	0.00953	0.00646	0.00316
Intercept	0.04992	0.12503	0.07444	0.01951
R^2	0.992	0.990	0.980	0.989
Rate (min^{-1})	3.6×10^{-2}	2.2×10^{-2}	1.5×10^{-2}	0.7×10^{-2}

catalytic power of the nickel tin oxide is due to its lower band gap value compared to nickel oxide and tin oxide.

Conclusion

The study has demonstrated the feasibility of synthesis of pure NiSnO_3 nano powder using a simple co-precipitation process. The NiSnO_3 crystalline formation is completed at 850 °C. The NiSnO_3 powders was characterized by using XRD and the particle size calculated based on Scherrer equation lies between 87 to 118 nm. NiSnO_3 synthesized is found to be very good photocata-

lyst under visible light condition as evidenced from the photo-bleaching of methyl orange solution. The highest rate constant was observed for using nickel tin oxide as catalyst ($3.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$) rather than using nickel oxide ($0.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$), tin oxide ($1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$) individually and their 1 : 1 combinations ($2.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$). The enhanced photocatalytic activity of NiSnO_3 is its lower band gap value (3.02 eV) compared to nickel oxide (3.50 eV) and tin oxide (3.60 eV). Further studies will focus on the effect on photocatalytic activity with varying load of photocatalyst (NiSnO_3) and its thermal and chemical stability.

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